

The Influence of Leadership Style, Supervisory and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Motivation as an Intervening Variable (Descriptive Study of Quantitative Analysis of Employee Performance at the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency)

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ABSTRACT: Based on the results of observations, that the level of absenteeism is still low, employee absences continue to increase every year, especially for the criteria for absences, sick, late and going home. This shows that the leadership is less than optimal in supervising its employees, it is found that there are still many employees who do not come to work due to permits, illness and are late for work and even go home early. Based on the Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 53 of 2010 concerning Discipline of Civil Servants Article 3 Point 11 which states that entering work and obeying the provisions of working hours. As a result, employees do not complete the work and often make mistakes over and over again. The purpose of this study in general is to analyze and describe the significant direct or indirect positive influence of leadership style, supervision and organizational culture on employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable. The research method used is to use path analysis (Part Analysis) to determine the direct or indirect effect of the variables studied. It is then used to analyze the extent to which the work motivation variable is able to mediate an increase in the quality of management information systems to improve employee performance and to what extent the work motivation variable is able to mediate the effect of leadership style on improving the performance of the Serang Regency Education and Culture Office Employees. The results obtained after the research was carried out were: 1) Based on the calculation results of SPSS v.25 Beta value due to the direct influence of leadership style on performance $\beta = 0.000$ the indirect effect of motivational mediating factors on the influence of leadership style on the performance of the employees of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency obtained value of $\beta = 0.215$. The comparison of the value of direct effect is smaller than the value of indirect effect which causes work motivation to be able to mediate the influence of leadership style on employee performance. 2). Based on the calculation results of SPSS v.25 Beta value due to the direct influence of supervision on performance $\beta = 0.155$. the indirect effect of the mediating motivational factor on the influence of supervision on the performance of the employees of the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency obtained the value of $\beta = -0.046$. Comparison of the value of direct effect is greater than the value of indirect effect which causes motivation to be unable to mediate the effect of supervision on employee performance. 3). Based on the calculation results of SPSS v.25 Beta value due to the direct influence of organizational culture on performance $\beta = 0.000$. the indirect effect of the mediating motivational factor on the influence of organizational culture on the performance of the employees of the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency obtained the value of $\beta = 0.243$. Comparison of values direct effect is smaller than value indirect effect that causes motivation to be able to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance

KEYWORDS: Employee performance, Leadership style, Motivation, Organizational culture, Supervision.

PRELIMINARY

The role of Human Resources (HR), namely employees / employees as a source of labor in an organizational unit is needed to produce quality products, both products in the form of goods or products in the form of services. Employee productivity is the center of attention in an effort to improve performance which affects the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization. Therefore employees play a very strategic role in an organization. In realizing its existence in order to achieve goals, an organization requires an effective human resource planning. "Human resources in the company are a key factor for the current running of the company

and the development of the company in the future which is one of the operational factors besides machinery, equipment, materials and funds" Rivai (2013).

The Office of Education and Culture is a government agency that has the task of carrying out some regional government affairs based on the principle of autonomy and assistance in the fields of education and culture. To carry out these tasks, the Office of Education and Culture, carries out functions including the formulation of technical policies in the field of education and culture. Implementation of government affairs and public services in the field of early childhood education and non-formal education, basic education and culture;

Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Mathis and Jackson (2010) "performance is basically what employees do and what they don't do". And according to Mangkunegara (2017), "performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him". Based on the initial survey at the research location, it was found that there was a tendency to decrease employee performance. The decline was marked by the lack of discipline of employees in carrying out their duties, this can be seen by the presence of several employees who did not come to the office on time, exercised during working hours at the Office of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.

An important element in an organization is the existence of a leader. Leadership is an abstract concept, but the results are real. Sometimes leadership leads to art, but often it is also related to science. Indrawijaya and Suprati (2008) state, "the success of an organization, both as a whole and as part of a group within the organization, is highly dependent on the quality of leadership contained in the organization concerned". Meanwhile Sulistyani (2008) argues that: "a leader is someone who leads other people by giving instructions, or by being interpreted more formally, that in carrying out leadership that person gives orders". The author observes some of the leadership issues in the Office of Education and Culture of Serang Regency, namely the lack of firm leadership in imposing sanctions on employees who are not disciplined. This causes a decrease in the performance of some employees.

In providing support and motivation to his subordinates, a leader has influence over his subordinates. Organizations need to know what motivates their employees, because this can be one of the determinants of whether or not the work given. Motivation is formed from employee attitudes in dealing with work situations in the organization. Hasibuan (2013) says that work motivation is "Providing driving force that creates enthusiasm for someone's work so that they want to work together, work effectively, and integrate with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction". The author observes some of the problems of motivation in the Office of Education and Culture of Serang Regency, namely that so far employees are less motivated because the results received by employees who are diligent with employees who work normally are the same, there is no difference in income received, both basic income and income additional allowance.

Another factor that influences employee performance is organizational culture. The purpose of a good organizational culture, of course, is to improve employee performance. Organizations with a strong culture will influence the behavior and effectiveness of employee performance. Employee performance will go according to the culture adopted in the organization. In addition, the application of culture within a company will also shape the character of employees by themselves in carrying out their duties and achieving the goals of the company. Organizational Culture is a characteristic that is upheld by the organization and serves as a role model for the organization as a differentiator between one organization and another or also as values and norms of behavior that are accepted and understood jointly by members of the organization as the basis for the rules of conduct contained in the organization. According to Effendi (2015) organizational culture is defined as norms, values, assumptions, beliefs, philosophies, organizational habits, and so on which were developed over a long period of time by the founders, leaders, and members of the organization which were socialized and taught to new members and applied in organizational activities thereby influencing the mindset, attitudes, and behavior of members of the organization in producing products, serving consumers, and achieving organizational goals. The author observes that some of the problems of organizational culture in the Office of Education and Culture of Serang Regency are the loss of the culture of respecting senior employees, especially by new employees.

In carrying out ongoing organizational activities, it is necessary to have supervision carried out by the leadership to the fullest so that employees can carry out their work duties properly, so that they can achieve organizational goals and increase the success of employee performance. Supervision refers to controlling activities. According to Effendi (2014) that "Control is to determine what is accomplished, evaluate it, and apply corrective measures, if needed, to ensure results in keeping with the plan. Control is to define what is to be achieved, evaluate it, and implement corrective steps, if needed, to ensure results are according to plan. Supervision is

said to be important because without good supervision it will certainly produce unsatisfactory goals, both for the organization itself and for the employees thus, supervision is carried out by the leadership maximally and thoroughly for subordinates by monitoring and measuring all activities that are being carried out can prevent the occurrence of irregularities in each activity and can achieve the goals set. Based on the observations that have been made by researchers, it is still seen that the supervisory function is not properly realized for employees. Lack of oversight function because the leadership is rarely in place and often participates in activities outside the service, one of these activities is outside service activities, namely participating in activities that are outside, not in the service office. Weak supervisory functions have an adverse impact on employees resulting in increased employee absenteeism. This can be seen from the level of employee absenteeism in 2018-2020 in Table 1.1 as follows:

Table 1.1. Employee Absentee Level of Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency for 2018-2020

Nu	Absence	Percentage		
		2018	2019	2020
1	Present	77,4	76,6	80,7
2	Sick	3,7	3,2	4,3
3	Permission	13,04	19,4	25,9
4	Late and Home Early	5,02	6,20	15,2

Source: Department of Education and Culture Kab. Serang 2021

Based on Table 1.1 above, it shows that the absenteeism rate for employee absences continues to increase every year, especially for the criteria for absenteeism, illness and tardiness and going home. This shows that the leadership is not optimal in supervising its employees, it is found that there are still many employees who are absent from work due to permits, illness and coming to work late and even leaving early. Based on the Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 53 of 2010 concerning the discipline of civil servants Article 3 Point 11 which states that entering work and complying with the provisions of working hours, punctuality in working hours applies from 07.30 - 16.00 WIB, but at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency there are still employees arriving late and there are employees during break hours and go straight home before working hours end. The level of employee absenteeism can also be used as a basis for measuring employee performance, the more employees who are absent, the level of leadership supervision is still low resulting in low employee performance.

At the Office of Education and Culture of Serang Regency, there are still quite large differences between the performance of one employee and the performance of another employee. This difference can occur because many employees work only to meet the minimum standard requirements that become their culture (only to fulfill the Main Performance Indicators), while there are other employees who can work actively, enthusiastically devoting themselves to the interests of the organization. To produce productive performance from each of these employees, a leader needs to provide motivation that can lead to the creation of a strong organizational culture, meaning that each employee must be able to independently, creatively and dynamically complete tasks assigned by the leadership to be completed on time.

Another phenomenon that occurs is the large number of studies on the performance of government employees who find that the results of the research vary. Hendrawati & Kurniawati, (2020) found that leadership style influences employee performance, where education, skills and talents possessed by leaders can improve employee performance. Whereas Setiyono, (2017) found that leadership style has no effect on employee performance where employees do not feel leaders who take the initiative and play a role in paying attention to the importance of costs and maintaining good communication so that it affects the quality of employee performance. It can be concluded that a leader can determine the high and low performance of an employee. Capability as a leader certainly has a very wide space in his leadership. His skills in handling each employee, his skills in making decisions, his skills in socializing, because a leader is a person who is able to unite all the characters of his employees to achieve organizational goals.

Edi Sugiyono and Rita Rahajeng (2022) with research on the influence of organizational culture, leadership style and job satisfaction on employee performance through employee motivation as an intervening variable in the food security, maritime and agriculture services of DKI Jakarta Province in 2020 found that there is a positive influence of Organizational Culture on Performance Employees with an R Square of 0.326 have a positive influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance with an R Square of 0.364. The results of the study of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Work Motivation are

positive with a mediating effect of a mediation coefficient of 0.315, and there is a positive influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with a mediation coefficient of 0.251.

Muhammad Oceano Fauzan and Fathiyah (2017) found results that organizational culture, leadership style, and supervision together through motivation on performance is 0.34%, the indirect effect is 0.0001% and the total effect is 0.34%. Thus, the variables of organizational culture, leadership style, supervision through motivation together contribute to the performance of employees of the Public Works Service (PU) of Batang Hari Jambi Regency.

Girsang, (2019) who found that organizational culture does not affect employee performance because employees do not care about the values that exist in the organization so that organizational culture does not become a guide for employees in doing work. It can be concluded that organizational culture can improve employee performance if an employee has values or principles in being responsible for his work besides that the organization also needs to emphasize organizational values such as the vision and mission of the organization which must be held tightly by employees.

Sugito Efendi & Suharsono, (2019) found Employee Motivation has an effect on employee performance, where employees get proper needs, feel safe in doing work, have close relationships with all employees, want to always receive appreciation, like to carry out challenging tasks, there is a desire to receive awards in the form of praise from superiors and opportunities for self-development through various education and training that can support careers in employees.

Evi Wahyuni (2015) with research on the Effects of Organizational Culture and Leadership Style on Employee Performance in the Financial Section of Public Sector Organizations with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable (Case Study of Tasikmalaya City Government Employees) found that there is a positive influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with R Square of 0.326 there is a positive influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance with an R Square of 0.364. The results of the study of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Work Motivation are positive with a mediating effect of a mediation coefficient of 0.315, and there is a positive influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with a mediation coefficient of 0.251.

Meanwhile, Dessy & Sanuddin, (2013) found that employee motivation has no effect on employee performance where unpleasant emotional states affect employee performance. Therefore the main key is during the recruitment process. How to find out the character of a prospective employee, his motivation or goals for work, what things he wants to give to the organization. So that his motivation in working helps the organization in achieving its goals.

Here the researcher can conclude that to improve employee performance, an organization needs to understand indicators such as organizational culture, leadership style, supervision and others. The next question is whether the Serang Regency Education and Culture Office has human resource management that is competent in the performance of its employees

On the basis of the conditions of leadership style, supervision, organizational culture and motivation and performance that are not yet optimal at the Serang District Office of Education and Culture, the author will conduct research to raise the issue of leadership style, supervision, organizational culture, motivation on employee performance with the title: "INFLUENCE LEADERSHIP STYLE, SUPERVISION AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN SERANG DISTRICT EDUCATION AND CULTURE OFFICE THROUGH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE".

THEORETICAL BASIS

Leadership Style

According to Siagian (2014), leadership style is a behavioral norm that is used by someone when that person tries to influence the behavior of others as seen by the leader. The achievement of the vision and mission of an organization will be determined by the leadership style of a leader in the organization. The leader as a locomotive to be followed by his subordinates.

Talking about style actually talks about "modality" in leadership. Modality can be interpreted as a leader who explores ways that are liked and used by someone as a vehicle for carrying out their leadership. A person's leadership style will be identical to the leadership type of the person concerned. Someone who occupies a leadership position has the capacity to read the situation he is facing appropriately and adjust his leadership style to suit the demands of the situation he is facing, even though the adjustment may only be temporary.

Leadership style is the basis for classifying leadership types. The leadership style according to Hasibuan (2013) is as follows:

a) Authoritarian Leadership

Authoritarian leadership is if the power or authority, most absolutely remains with the leadership or adheres to a centralized system of authority. Decision-making and policies are only determined by the leader himself, subordinates are not included to provide suggestions, ideas and considerations in the decision-making process.

b) Participatory leadership

Participative leadership is when the leadership is carried out in a persuasive way, creating harmonious cooperation, fostering loyalty and participation of subordinates so that they feel they belong to the company.

c) Delegative Leadership

Delegative leadership when a leader delegates authority to subordinates rather completely. Thus, subordinates can make decisions and policies freely or freely in exercising power.

The three types of leadership are carried out in the interests of the leader. The interest in question is in the implementation of tasks, cooperative relations and the results achieved. The implementation of the three patterns should be implemented together because if done together, the tasks ordered by the leader will be achieved. The three types of leadership above in practice can be said to complement each other, the three types of leadership can be adapted to the circumstances of the situation which will produce leadership that looks effective.

The definition of leadership style from various experts can be briefly described that leadership style is a way or pattern of action in the role of a leader who has the behavior and characteristics of each with the aim of increasing the productivity of his subordinates and influencing subordinates/employees to achieve the goals set. set. In this leadership style can direct subordinates to follow the rules that are in the organization. Each leadership style cannot be changed by coercion, but is a situation to change behavior where when it will be necessary in a particular goal or activity to change behavior according to the situation.

Sanusi (2015) developed a bloom taxonomy theory by adding belief skills, operational skills, and leadership skills. Leadership skills are skills to do something in leadership. By adding these skills, it will become more complete what humans do as well as managerial skills. Leadership skills can be seen through various managerial skills, namely:

- a. Technical skills, namely the skills to use techniques in carrying out their duties.
- b. Human skills are communication skills.
- c. Conceptual skill is the ability to view the organization as a unified system.
- d. Design skills, namely the ability to solve problems.

Leaders who have the behavior to invite subordinates to follow them are the styles that are owned by each leader. The behavior of a leader can be known only by knowing his personality. If subordinates or employees always pay attention to the leader's behavior, it may be seen that the leader has a different leadership style when compared to the previous leader. A leader who is in an agency has a leadership style that can direct his subordinates or also his people to keep abreast of developments in the world of politics by providing political education so they are not blind in politics.

According to Siagian (2014), indicators of leadership style that can be seen are as follows:

- a. A climate of mutual trust
- b. Appreciation of subordinates' ideas
- c. Consider the feelings of subordinates
- d. Attention to work comfort for subordinates
- e. Concern for the welfare of subordinates
- f. Recognition of the status of subordinates appropriately and proportionally

Siagian's six indicators are effectiveness factors in the world of leadership which are influenced by behavior that causes subordinates to like coming to him to convey various problems they face. Indicators from Siagian are very useful for studying the extent to which a leader's attitude can bring change to subordinates by calculating from a performance in completing their tasks.

Supervision

Supervision can be interpreted as a process to ensure that organizational and management goals are achieved. This relates to ways of making activities according to plan with the instructions that have been given and with the principles that have been outlined. (Robert J. Mockler: 2013), Supervision explained by Robert J. Mockler has explained the essential elements of the supervision

process, namely a systematic effort to set implementation standards and planning objectives designing information systems, feedback, comparing real activities with standards previously set.

The term supervision in Indonesian comes from the word "watch out", so that supervision is an activity of supervising only. Sarwoto provides a definition of supervision as follows: "Supervision is the activity of managers who make sure that the work is carried out in accordance with the established plans and or the desired results".

Judging from the type, this supervision has three types of supervision, namely:

- a. Preliminary supervision (steering controls). These controls are designed to address problems or deviations from standards or objectives and allow corrections to be made before a particular activity is completed.
- b. Supervision is carried out together with the implementation of activities (Concurrent Controls). Supervision is carried out during an activity in progress. This type of supervision is a process in which certain aspects must be fulfilled before activities can be continued or become a kind of "double check" tool that better guarantees the determination of the implementation of an activity.
- c. Feedback supervision is supervision that measures the results of certain activities that have been completed. Supervision is a process where the leader wants to know whether the results of the work carried out by his subordinates are in accordance with the plans, orders, goals or policies that have been determined. (Handayani: 2002)

Seeing from these types of supervision, a good government needs to supervise its subordinates by looking at the process of program implementation or the results of activities that have been completed.

According to Terry (2014), Supervision is an activity to make evaluations and corrections to a result achieved, with the intention that the result is in accordance with the plan (Control is to determine what is accomplished evaluate it, and apply corrective measures, if needed to result in keeping with the plan).

To further improve the optimization of supervision according to Terry (2014) there are four factors that need attention, namely: work standards, financing, executive reports, and costs. Furthermore, Terry sets out four steps/indicators that must be carried out in the controlling process, namely:

1. Setting Standards (Defining standards or basis for supervision).
2. Measuring performance (assessment of work results).
3. Compare performance with work standards, and determine the comparison/difference (appropriateness).
4. Correction of deviations that occur as a corrective action (corrective action).

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is a shared perception held by members of the organization, and is a system of shared meaning (Robbins: 2017). Organization is a system of roles, flow of activities and processes (patterns of work relations) and involves several people as executors of tasks made to achieve common goals.

Important things that can be considered in the elements of organizational culture, namely patterns of beliefs, values and ways that have been learned based on the experience of the history of the organization. These beliefs, values and ways tend to be embodied in the material arrangements and behavior of organizational members.

Sanusi (2017) states that there is a set of values that must be realized in human life that must be instilled so that humans have value in their lives. These values are formulated in six categories of "value systems", namely (1) Theological Values; which is reflected among others in the pillars of faith, pillars of Islam, monotheism, worship, sincerity, istighfar, sincerity, repentance, ijtihad, special and istiqomah; (2) Ethical-Legal Values; which is reflected among others in respect, kindness, humility, loyalty, trustworthiness, honesty, responsibility, good faith, loyalty, fairness, peace, patience, forgiveness, help, tolerance and harmony; (3) Aesthetic Value; manifested, among others, in good, clean, beautiful, beautiful, sweet, attractive, harmonious, romantic, and loving; (4) Logical-rational value; which is manifested, among others, in logic/match between facts & conclusions, precise, appropriate, clear, real, identical/characteristic, process, circumstances/conclusions match; (5) Physical-physiological value; what is clearly manifested, its elements, functions, dimensions, strength, change, location, origin, cause and effect; (6) Teleological value; which is manifested in useful, beneficial, according to its function, developing/advanced, organized/disciplined, integrative, productive, effective, efficient, accountable, innovative.

Employees who already understand the overall values of the organization will then make these values an organizational personality. These values and beliefs will make their daily behavior at work, so that it will become individual performance. Human

resources are supported by systems, technology, corporate strategy and logistics, each good individual performance will lead to good organizational performance.

Of the various concepts of organizational culture, a description is found. Organizational culture as a pattern and model consisting of beliefs, and values that give meaning to members of an organization and rules for members to behave in the organization. According to Davis in Ismail Nawawi Uha (2013), every organization has its own meaning to the word culture itself, including identity, ideology, ethos, pattern of existence, rules, center of interest, philosophy of purpose, spirit, sources of information, style, vision, and method. Robbins (2017), juga menyebutkan bahwa budaya organisasi memiliki beberapa karakteristik yang akan menjadi budaya internal di dalam sebuah organisasi antara lain sebagai berikut :

- 1) Individual initiative, namely the extent to which the organization gives freedom to each employee in expressing opinions or ideas in carrying out their duties and functions. The individual initiative needs to be appreciated by the group or the leadership of an organization as far as ideas are concerned to advance and develop the organization.
- 2) Direction, namely the extent to which the leadership of an organization can clearly create the desired goals and expectations, so that employees can understand them and all activities carried out by employees lead to the achievement of organizational goals. The goals and expectations are clearly stated in the vision and mission.
- 3) Integration, namely the extent to which an organization can encourage organizational units to work in a coordinated way. Coordination is the process of integrating objectives and activities in separate units (departments or functional areas) of an organization to achieve goals.
- 4) Management support, namely the extent to which organizational leaders can provide clear communication or direction, assistance and support to employees. This support can be in the form of efforts to develop the ability of employees such as conducting training.
- 5) Control, namely the existence of supervision from the leaders of the employees by using the rules that have been set for the smooth running of the organization. Supervision can be defined as a process to ensure that organizational goals are achieved.
- 6) The reward system, namely the extent to which the allocation of rewards (such as salary increases, promotions, and so on) is based on employee performance, not vice versa based on seniority, favoritism, and so on.
- 7) Patterns of communication, namely the extent to which communication within an organization that is limited by a formal hierarchy of authority can work well. Communication itself is the process of transferring understanding or information from one person to another. Good communication is communication that can meet the needs of its target, so that it can ultimately provide more effective results.
- 8) Tolerance of conflict, namely the extent to which employees are encouraged to openly express conflict and criticism in order to advance the organization, and how does the organization respond to this conflict.
- 9) Tolerance for risky actions, namely the extent to which employees are encouraged to be able to act aggressively, be innovative and take risks in taking opportunities that can advance and develop the organization. The intended risky actions are all consequences arising from the implementation of the duties and functions carried out by employees.

Employee Performance

Performance is a system used to assess and find out whether an employee has carried out his work as a whole, or is a combination of work results (what a person must achieve) and competence (how a person achieves it). (Sedarmayanti: 2017),

Employee performance can be defined as activities that are officially recognized as part of the job and that contribute to organizational goals. There are two dimensions of performance: the dimension of action known as the behavioral aspect and the outcome dimension known as the performance aspect. Behavioral aspects of performance are considered to be consistent with work situations and job specifications, which are then turned into means of achieving organizational goals and objectives, that is, outcome dimensions or performance aspects. (Maamari, and Saheb: 2018)

Another opinion suggests that a person's performance is determined by his ability and motivation to carry out the work. Furthermore, it is said that the implementation of work is determined by the interaction of abilities and motivation. (Ismail Nawawi: 2013).

The term performance comes from the word Job Performance or Actual Performance, namely work performance or actual performance of an employee/employee, so the meaning of performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. (Mankunegara : 2017)

"Performance or performance is a picture of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity program or policy in realizing the goals, objectives, vision and mission of the organization as outlined through the strategic planning of an organization." (Moeheriono: 2014),

So based on the opinion of the experts above that performance is the result of the performance of a person or group of people measured over a certain period of time based on a predetermined agreement.

To reinforce and clarify how performance appraisal in an organization can produce quality individuals, Malayu S P Hasibuan (2013) states that performance appraisal is assessing the ratio with quality and quantity standards produced by each employee.

In an organization, employees must have the skills to be able to do/do what we learn in Sanusi's theory called operational skills (Sanusi, 2016). Sanusi argues that operational skills are very important because people learn not only to know, to love, to have the will to believe in all of that but have to grow and think further, namely whether to do it or not in their daily life, so there needs to be an emphasis on operational skills (skills to carry out /work). operational skills are needed to become a person who is firm in holding the basic principles but fluent in acting, because he already has a variety of skills from the lowest skill level to the highest skill level. These skill levels include cognitive, affective, psychomotor, believing skills, and operational skills (Sanusi: 2016).

Performance indicators are something that will be calculated and measured. In setting performance indicators, a form of measurement must be identified that will assess the results or outcomes obtained from the activities carried out. This performance indicator is used to present that the employee's day to day performance is making progress towards the goals and objectives in the strategic plan. Employee performance can be measured in several ways. This size reflects the size of the performance. The elements or indicators assessed are:

1. Quantity of Work.

It is the volume or amount of workload or the amount that must be completed by an employee, measured quantitatively by the ability to achieve targets or work results in accordance with what is charged.

2. Quality of Work.

It is the degree to which the work is good or bad for this employee, which can be seen in terms of accuracy, neatness of work, speed of completing work, skills and dexterity of employees at work.

3. Work knowledge (Job Knowledge).

Is the process of placing an employee according to his educational background or expertise in a job. This can be seen from the ability of employees to understand things related to the tasks they perform.

4. Teamwork (Team Work)

It is a collaborative effort between fellow employees in completing a job. Collaboration is not only limited to vertical or collaboration between employees, but horizontal cooperation is also a very important factor in organizational life, namely where organizational leaders and their employees establish a conducive relationship and produce mutually beneficial relationships.

5. Initiative / Creativity (Creativity).

It is the ability of an employee to complete each job in ways or initiatives that are considered effective and efficient and capable of creating change. Changes to make improvements for the betterment of the organization. (Mankunegara : 2017),

Motivation

Motivation is a condition (energy) that moves within an individual directed to achieve organizational goals. (Mankunegara : 2017),

The theory of motivation is understood so that leaders are able to identify what motivates employees to work, the relationship between work behavior and motivation, and why high achieving employees. The theory of motivation in this study is based on achievement theory. Prof. Dr. David C. McClelland, an American psychologist from Harvard University, in his theory of motivation suggests that a person's productivity is largely determined by the mental virus that exists in him.

Mental virus is a mental condition that encourages a person to be able to achieve his maximum performance. The mental virus in question consists of three driving needs, namely:

1. The need for achievement (Need of Achievement), is the need to achieve success, which is measured based on the standard of opportunity in a person. This need is closely related to work and directs behavior in efforts to achieve certain achievements.

2. Need for Affiliation, is the need for warmth and support in relation to other people. This need directs behavior to establish intimate relationships with other people.
3. The need for power, is the need to control and influence situations and other people in order to become dominant and controlling.

This need causes the person concerned to pay less attention to the feelings of others. Based on McClelland's theory, he explained that it is very important to develop a manager's mental virus by developing employee potential through an effective work environment so that high quality company productivity is realized and the main goals of the organization are achieved.

On the basis of McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory, it can be concluded that there are three factors or dimensions of motivation, namely motives, expectations and incentives. The three dimensions of motivation are briefly described in the following discussion:

1) Motive

Motive is a stimulant of desire and driving force of the will to work. Each motive has a specific goal to be achieved. An impulse within each person, the level of reasons or motives that move it describes the level to achieve something.

2) Hope

Hope is the possibility of achieving something with a certain action. An employee is motivated to carry out a high level of effort if the employee believes the effort will lead to a good performance appraisal. A good judgment will encourage organizational rewards (giving employees hope) such as bonuses, raises, or promotions, and these rewards will satisfy employee personal goals.

3) Incentives

Incentives given to employees greatly affect motivation and work productivity. This is in accordance with what was concluded by Edwin Locke in Mangkunegara (2017), that incentives in the form of money if the gift is related to the purpose of carrying out tasks greatly affect the increase in employee productivity. Leaders need to make plans to provide incentives in the form of adequate money so that employees are motivated for their performance and are able to achieve maximum productivity.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research was conducted at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency, Block Jalak No.174, RT.5/RW.9, Panancangan, Kec. Cipocok Jaya, City of Serang, Banten 42124

The research method used is the questionnaire method with Path Analysis techniques. This technique is used to measure the relationship between Leadership Style (X1), Supervision (X2), and Organizational Culture (X3) with Employee Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z)

The relationship between the dependent variable (Y) and the independent variables (X1; X2; X3) and the Intervening Variable (Z) can be seen in the constellation model below:

Figure 3.1 Path Diagrams

Information:

X1 = Leadership Style

X2 = Supervision

X3 = Organizational Culture

Y = Employee Performance

Z = Motivation

To find out whether there is influence between Leadership Style, Supervision and Organizational Culture, with employee performance through motivation (Z), regression analysis techniques are used. The regression line equation is:

Substructural structural equation 1:

$$Y = \rho_{YX1}X1 + \rho_{YX2}X2 + \rho_{YX3}X3 + \epsilon1$$

Structural substructural equation 2:

$$Z = \rho_{ZX1}X1 + \rho_{ZX2}X2 + \rho_{ZX3}X3 + \epsilon2$$

Structural substructural equation 3:

$$Z = \rho_{YZ}Y + \epsilon1$$

To require mediation hypothesis testing can be done with a procedure developed by Sobel (1982) and known as the Sobel test / sobel test. (Ghozali: 2018),. The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y through Z. The indirect effect of X to Y through Z is calculated by multiplying the path X1 to Z (ρ_{ZX1}) by the path Z to Y (ρ_{YZ}), multiplying the path X2 to Z (ρ_{ZX2}) by the Z to Y path (ρ_{YZ}) and multiplying the X3 to Z path (ρ_{ZX3}) by the Z to Y path (ρ_{YZ}).

The standard error coefficients of ρ_{ZX1} and ρ_{YZ} are written with Se_{ZX1} and Se_{YZ} , the magnitude of the standard error coefficients of the indirect effects of ρ_{ZX2} and ρ_{YZ} are written with Se_{ZX2} and Se_{YZ} and the magnitude of the standard error coefficients of the indirect effects of ρ_{ZX3} and ρ_{YZ} are written with Se_{ZX3} and Se_{YZ} with the following formula:

$$Se_{ZX1}YZ = \sqrt{\rho_{ZX1}^2 \cdot Se_1^2 + \rho_{YZ}^2 \cdot Se_2^2 + Se_1^2 + Se_2^2}$$

$$Se_{ZX2}YZ = \sqrt{\rho_{ZX2}^2 \cdot Se_1^2 + \rho_{YZ}^2 \cdot Se_2^2 + Se_1^2 + Se_2^2}$$

$$Se_{ZX3}YZ = \sqrt{\rho_{ZX3}^2 \cdot Se_1^2 + \rho_{YZ}^2 \cdot Se_2^2 + Se_1^2 + Se_2^2}$$

To test the significance of the indirect effect. then we need to calculate the value of t with the following formula:

$$t = \frac{\rho_{ZX1}YZ}{Se_{ZX1}YZ}$$

$$t = \frac{\rho_{ZX2}YZ}{Se_{ZX2}YZ}$$

$$t = \frac{\rho_{ZX3}YZ}{Se_{ZX3}YZ}$$

Hypothesis:

H0 : b = 0 , there is no mediating effect

Ha : b ≠ 0 , there is a mediating effect

Test criteria:

If t count > t table, H0 is rejected, Ha is accepted

If t count < t table, H0 is accepted, Ha is rejected

Or

If -t count < -t table, H0 is rejected, Ha is accepted

If -t count > -t table, H0 is accepted, Ha is rejected

In this study the value of r2 was searched using the SPSS for Windows Release 25.0 computer program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Path Analysis of the Influence of Leadership Style, Supervision and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

Table 4.1. Sub-Structure Path Test 1.1

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.908 ^a	.825	.811	3.4801	2.132

a. Predictors: (Constant), BudayaOrganisasi(X3), Pengawasan(X2), GayaKepemimpinan(X1)

b. Dependent Variable: KinerjaPegawai(Y)

Table 4.2. Sub-Structure Path Test 1.2

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	29.402	6.257		4.540	.000		
	GayaKepemimpinan(X1)	1.374	.113	1.416	12.195	.000	.334	2.998
	Pengawasan(X2)	-.138	.095	-.123	-1.452	.155	.629	1.591
	BudayaOrganisasi(X3)	-.564	.083	-.727	-6.796	.000	.392	2.554

a. Dependent Variable: KinerjaPegawai(Y)

It can be seen that in the sig column in table 4.31 coefficients, the sig values are 0.000, 0.155 and 0.000, it turns out that the sig value is 0.000 < 0.05, then Ho is rejected H1 is accepted meaning that the path analysis coefficient on the leadership style variable is significant to employee performance. And the sig value is 0.155 > 0.05, then Ho is accepted H2 is rejected, meaning that the path analysis coefficient of the monitoring variable is not significant to the employee performance variable. And the sig value is 0.000 < 0.05, then Ho is rejected. H3 is accepted, meaning that the coefficient of path analysis of organizational culture variables is significant to employee performance variables.

To find out the contribution of how much influence other variables have on employee performance (ε1) can be determined in the following way :

$$(\epsilon 1) = \sqrt{1 - R^2} = \sqrt{1 - 0,825} = \sqrt{0,175} = 0,4183 = 41,83\%$$

Then the value of (ε1) the path coefficient of other variables on employee performance at the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency is 41.83%. So the path equation is:

$$Y = 1.416 \text{ leadership style} - 0.123 \text{ supervision} - 0.727 \text{ organizational culture} + 0.4183$$

Figure 4.1. Causal relationship in sub structure 1

1. Path Analysis of the Influence of Leadership Style, Supervision and Organizational Culture on Work Motivation

Table 4.3. Sub-Structure Path Test 2.1

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.916 ^a	.839	.826	4.1419	1.881

a. Predictors: (Constant), BudayaOrganisasi(X3), Pengawasan(X2), GayaKepemimpinan(X1)
 b. Dependent Variable: Motivasi(Z)

Table 4.4. Sub-Structure Path Test 2.2

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.350	7.446			.047	.963		
	GayaKepemimpinan(X1)	.584	.134	.485	4.354	.000	.334	2.998	
	Pengawasan(X2)	-.146	.113	-.105	-1.291	.204	.829	1.591	
	BudayaOrganisasi(X3)	.527	.099	.547	5.328	.000	.392	2.554	

a. Dependent Variable: Motivasi(Z)

It can be seen that in the sig column in table 4.4 the coefficients get a sig value of 0.000, 0.204 and 0.000. It turns out that the sig value of 0.000 < 0.05, then H0 is rejected H4 is accepted, meaning that the path analysis coefficient on the leadership style variable is significant to motivation. Sig value 0.204 > 0.05, then H0 is accepted and H5 is rejected, meaning that the path analysis coefficient on the control variable is not significant to the motivational variable. And the sig value of 0.000 < 0.05, then H0 is rejected and H6 is accepted, meaning that the path analysis coefficient on the organizational culture variable is significant to the motivational variable.

To find out the contribution of how much influence other variables have on employee performance (ε2) can be determined in the following way:

$$(\epsilon_2) = \sqrt{1 - R^2} = \sqrt{1 - 0,839} = \sqrt{0,161} = 0,401 = 40,1\%$$

Then the value (ε2) of the path coefficient of other variables on the motivation of employees of the Serang Regency Education and Culture Office is 40.1%. So the path equation is:

$$Z = 0.485 \text{ leadership style} - 0.105 \text{ supervision} + 0.547 \text{ organizational culture} + 0.401$$

Figure 4.2. Causal relationship in sub structure 2

1. Path Analysis of the Influence of Motivation on Performance

Table 4.5. Sub-Structure Path Test 3.1

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.444 ^a	.197	.177	7.2638	1.882

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi(Z)
 b. Dependent Variable: KinerjaPegawai(Y)

Table 4.6. Sub-Structure Path Test 3.2

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	56.373	9.327		6.044	.000		
	Motivasi(Z)	.358	.113	.444	3.171	.003	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pegawai(Y)

Based on table 4.6 above, it can be seen that the results of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable are as follows: Effect of motivation (Z) on employee performance (Y)

From the data processing above, the path coefficient value (P_{YZ}) is 0.444. This means that if the value (Z) of work motivation increases, then the variable level (Y) of employee performance will increase. Variable Z has a significant level of 0.003 < 0.05 so it can be said that the relationship between Z and Y is significant.

To find out the contribution of how much influence other variables have on employee performance (ε₃) can be determined in the following way:

$$(\epsilon_3) = \sqrt{1 - R^2} = \sqrt{1 - 0,197} = \sqrt{0,803} = 0,896 = 89,6\%$$

Then the value of (ε₃) the path coefficient of other variables on the performance of Serang District Education and Culture Office employees is 89.6%. So the path equation is:

$$Y = P_{YZ} + \epsilon_3 \text{ Employee Performance} = 0.444 \text{ work motivation} + 0.896$$

Figure 4.3. Causal relationship in sub-structure 3

From the picture of the causal relationship between sub-structures 1, 2 and 3, an empirical path diagram for the Intervening model is obtained as explained in the following figure:

Figure 4.4. Intervening model path diagram

Table 4.7. Summary of model parameter estimation results

Model	Path coefficient	T	P	R
1. Sub-structure 1 (X₁, X₂, X₃ Ke Y)				
X1 (PYX ₁)	1,416	12,195	0,000	0,908
X2 (PYX ₂)	-0,123	-1,452	0,155	
X3 (PYX ₃)	-0,727	-6,786	0,000	
2. Sub-structure 2 (X₁, X₂, X₃ Ke Z)				
X1 (PZX ₁)	0,485	4,354	0,000	0,916
X2 (PZX ₂)	-0,105	-1,291	0,204	
X3 (PZX ₃)	0,547	5,328	0,000	
3. Sub-structure 3 (Z ke Y)				
Z (PYZ)	0,444	3,171	0,003	0,444

Outcome of Indirect Influence

From the table and figure above, it can be seen that the indirect effects are:

- 1) The indirect effect of leadership style on employee performance through work motivation as an intervening variable.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (PYX_1) &= 1,416 \\
 &= (PZX_1) \times (PYZ) \\
 &= (0,485) \times (0,444) \\
 &= 0,21534
 \end{aligned}$$

From the calculation above it can be concluded that the motivational variable is able to mediate the relationship of leadership style to employee performance of 0.21534.

- 2) Indirect influence or indirect effect of supervision on employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (PYX_2) &= -0,123 \\
 &= (PZX_2) \times (PYZ) \\
 &= (-0,105) \times (0,444) \\
 &= -0,04662
 \end{aligned}$$

From the above calculations it can be concluded that the motivational variable is able to mediate the relationship from supervision to employee performance of -0.04662.

- 3) Indirect influence or indirect effect of organizational culture on employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable. (PYX₃) = -0,727

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (PZX_3) \times (PYZ) \\
 &= (0,547) \times (0,444) \\
 &= 0,242868
 \end{aligned}$$

From the calculation above it can be concluded that the motivational variable is able to mediate the relationship from organizational culture to employee performance of 0.242868.

Based on the various data analyzes above, it can be summarized in the table below:

Table 4.8. Direct and Indirect Influence

Variable	Direct Influence	Significant	Variabel	Indirect Influence	Significant
X1 against Y	1,416	0,000 (significant)	(X1 against Z) (Z against Y)	0,21534	significant
X2 against Y	-0,123	0,155 (Not significant)	(X2 against Z) (Z against Y)	-0,04662	Not significant
X3 against Y	-0,727	0,000 (significant)	(X3 against Z) (Z against Y)	0,242868	significant
Z against Y	0,444	0,003 (significant)			

Based on the test using SPSS, an indirect effect of each of the 3 variables was obtained on the Performance of the Serang Regency Education and Culture Office Employees through Motivation with the result that for Leadership Style there is an indirect effect on Employee Performance through Motivation. And there is a significant relationship between motivation and employee performance at the Education and Culture Office.

Then for the indirect effect of Supervision on Employee Performance of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency through motivation there is no indirect effect. Due to the relationship between Supervision on Motivation there is no significant effect, although for Motivation on the Performance of Employees of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency there is a significant influence.

And for the indirect effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency through motivation, there is a significant influence. Because there is a significant influence between Organizational Culture on Motivation, and for Motivation on the Performance of Employees of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency there is also a significant influence.

Detecting Influence (Sobel Test)

To test whether the intervening variable is significant or not, testing can be carried out using the Sobel test. With the following steps:

a. The mediating effect of leadership style on employee performance through work motivation

1) Calculate the value of the standard error of the indirect effect.

$$\begin{aligned}
 SeZX_1YZ &= \sqrt{\rho ZX_1^2 \cdot Se_1^2 + \rho YZ^2 \cdot Se_2^2 + Se_1^2 + Se_2^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,444)^2 \cdot (0,113)^2 + (0,485)^2 \cdot (0,113)^2 + (0,113)^2 + (0,113)^2} \\
 &\quad \sqrt{(0,197136) \cdot (0,012769) + (0,235225) \cdot (0,012769) + (0,012769) + (0,012769)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,00251545536) + (0,003003588025) + (0,012769) + (0,012769)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,031057043385)} \\
 &= 0,17623
 \end{aligned}$$

2. Determine the calculated t value

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= \frac{\rho ZX_1YZ}{SeZX_1YZ} \\
 t &= \frac{0,21534}{0,17623} = 1,222
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the value of t count (1.222) is smaller than t table with a significance level of 0.05 which is equal to 1.684, it can be concluded that it is significant. So it can be concluded that motivation does not mediate the relationship between leadership style and employee performance and is significant.

b. The mediating effect of supervision on employee performance through motivation.

1. Calculate the value of the standard error of the indirect effect.

$$\begin{aligned}
 SeZX_2YZ &= \sqrt{\rho ZX_2^2 \cdot Se_1^2 + \rho YZ^2 \cdot Se_2^2 + Se_1^2 + Se_2^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,444)^2 \cdot (0,095)^2 + (-0,105)^2 \cdot (0,113)^2 + (0,095)^2 + (0,113)^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,197136) \cdot (0,009025) + (0,011025) \cdot (0,012769) + (0,009025) + (0,012769)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,0017791524) + (0,000140778225) + (0,009025) + (0,012769)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,023713930625)} \\
 &= 0,15399
 \end{aligned}$$

2. Determine the calculated t value

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= \frac{\rho ZX_2YZ}{SeZX_2YZ} \\
 t &= \frac{0,04662}{0,15399} = 0,303
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the value of t count (0.303) is smaller than t table with a significance level of 0.05 which is equal to 1.684, it can be concluded that it is significant. So it can be concluded that motivation does not mediate the supervisory relationship with employee performance and is significant.

c. The mediating effect of organizational culture on employee performance through motivation.

1. Calculate the value of the standard error of the indirect effect.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Se_{ZX_3YZ} &= \sqrt{\rho ZX_3^2 \cdot Se_1^2 + \rho YZ^2 \cdot Se_2^2 + Se_1^2 + Se_2^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,444)^2 \cdot (0,083)^2 + (0,547)^2 \cdot (0,113)^2 + (0,083)^2 + (0,113)^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,197136) \cdot (0,006889) + (0,299209) \cdot (0,012769) + (0,006889) + (0,012769)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,001358090571) + (0,003820599721) + (0,006889) + (0,012769)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0,024836690292)} \\
 &= 0,1576
 \end{aligned}$$

2. Determine the calculated t value

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= \frac{\rho ZX_3YZ}{Se_{ZX_3YZ}} \\
 t &= \frac{0,242868}{0,1576} = 1,541
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the value of t count (1.541) is smaller than t table with a significance level of 0.05 which is equal to 1.684, it can be concluded that it is significant. So it can be concluded that motivation does not mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance and is significant.

CONCLUSION

1. Leadership style has a positive and significant direct effect on the work motivation of employees of the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency. This means that improving the quality of management information systems will affect the increase in work motivation of employees of the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.
2. Supervision has no direct and significant effect on the work motivation of employees of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency. This means that an increase in Leadership Style will not affect the increase in work motivation of employees of the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.
3. Organizational culture has a positive and significant direct effect on work motivation of employees of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency. This means that an increase in Organizational Culture will affect the increase in work motivation of employees of the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.
4. Leadership style has a direct positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Serang Regency Education and Culture Office. This means that an increase in leadership style will affect the increase in the performance of employees of the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency.
5. Supervision has no direct and insignificant effect on the performance of employees of the Serang District Education and Culture Office. This means that an increase in Supervision will not affect the increase in the performance of employees of the Serang District Education and Culture Office.
6. Organizational culture has a positive and significant direct effect on the performance of employees of the Serang District Education and Culture Office. This means that an increase in organizational culture will affect the increase in employee performance at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.
7. Motivation has a positive and significant direct effect on the performance of employees of the Serang Regency Education and Culture Office. This means that an increase in employee motivation will affect the increase in employee performance at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.
8. Leadership style has a direct effect on motivation and motivation also has a direct effect on employee performance so that an increase in employee motivation is able to mediate an increase in employee performance at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency

9. Supervision has no direct effect on motivation and motivation also has a direct effect on employee performance so that an increase in employee motivation has not been able to mediate an increase in employee performance at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency
10. Organizational culture has a direct effect on motivation and motivation also has a direct effect on employee performance so that an increase in employee motivation is able to mediate an increase in employee performance at the Department of Education and Culture of Serang Regency.
11. Looking at the significance of F obtained through the F test using SPSS, which is equal to 67.635, it is known that the variables of Leadership Style, Supervision, and Organizational Culture simultaneously affect motivation. This means that the motivation score is determined by the variable X. Even if viewed partially, only Leadership Style and Organizational Culture have a significant effect, while Supervision has no effect. This means that there is intervention from variable X, this means that motivation will always pay attention to the state of employee performance or there is an indirect influence of leadership style, supervision and organizational culture on employee performance through motivation at the Education and Culture Office of Serang Regency.

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